

Lung Region Segmentation and 3D Visualization from CT Scans: A Reproducible Python Implementation

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Abstract

Current segmentation and precise RECIST practises are carried out either manually or semi-automatically, aside from possible human error in the loop, this takes up valuable time and resources. Hence, this paper showcases a fully automated methodology for the detection and 3D segmentation of non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC). The used method is from a nature communications paper that presents this method along with actual figures, institutions' datasets validations and a clinical trial setting. This is a Python step by step tutorial and explanation of the aforementioned automated method for the user to implement into their projects. This paper presents the code, its corresponding output along with the process explanation. Additionally, there is also a 3D interactive model created after all the code implementation for a better look at the provided lungs' images.

Key words: *Python, code implementation, 3D, CT scans, Segmentation, Automated, code explanation*

Introduction

Lung cancer is the deadliest cancer worldwide, representing 18.4% of the total cancer deaths in 2018¹. Automated methods for the detection and segmentation of lung nodules have been developed using medical imaging and computer vision. However, the detection and segmentation of non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), which takes up 85% of all lung cancer cases, continue to be a challenging task. NSCLC is a type of lung cancer that is different from small cell lung cancer (SCLC) in terms of its cell type, growth rate, and treatment². Medical imaging, particularly computed tomography (CT), is used in radiotherapy to accurately localise tumours and measure electron densities for the purpose of calculating treatment doses³. Errors might result in over- or under-irradiation of the tumour and/or healthy tissue, therefore precise segmentation of the tumour and organs at risk is also crucial. According to estimates, a 1 mm change in the tumour segmentation might have a 15% impact on radiotherapy dosage predictions^{4,5}. The detection and segmentation of NSCLC are critical for patient management, status evaluation, and quantitative image research.

Lesion and organ at risk segmentation for radiation oncologists and the measurement of lesions within the Response Evaluation Criteria in Solid Tumours (RECIST) framework for radiologists are both essential and time-consuming manual tasks for radiotherapy planning⁶. At the moment,

these segmentations and the relevant RECIST measurements are performed manually or semi-automatically, wasting time and resources and subject to inter- and intra-observer variability⁷.

Another area that will immediately profit from automated lesion detection and delineation is radiomics, which is the high-throughput mining of quantitative information from medical pictures and their subsequent association with clinical and/or biological endpoints^{8,9}. Genomic research has the potential to support personalised treatment through diagnostic and predictive models based on the phenotypic traits of the region of interest (ROI) being explored¹⁰. Currently, the radiomics workflow's most time-consuming and laborious step is thought to be ROI segmentation¹¹.

The use of automated detection software that can quickly and accurately delineate NSCLC on thoracic CT scans is desirable, if not absolutely necessary, given these clinical and research needs for lung tumour segmentation. Applications and advantages include, but are not limited to: (1) Automated CT-based lung cancer screening; (2) Retrospective analysis of entire databases of patients who underwent thoracic CT in routine care for research; (3) Consistent and reproducible segmentations, which are crucial for planning and monitoring (radio)therapy, as well as for research; (4) Follow-up of treated primary lung cancer; and (5) Automation and acceleration of some clinical tasks.

It is necessary to first identify the lesion as an NSCLC before automating the segmentation of NSCLC tumours. The current clinical gold standard for identifying NSCLC is invasive tissue biopsy. High detection accuracy is necessary for an effective automated segmentation tool, though. In order to avoid invasive biopsies, software that can automatically segment NSCLC tumours could also be used as a detection method.

This method offers a pipeline for 3D volumetric segmentation and completely automated identification of lung tumors, which can be applied to a wide range of CT collection and reconstruction settings.

Literature review

In-depth study in the area of artificial intelligence (AI) for medical imaging analysis has been sparked by the recent development of machine learning techniques, together with advancements in the quality and storage of medical images^{12,13}. In order to handle issues like classification or segmentation, deep learning, a subset of AI-based artificial neural networks, has been effectively implemented on images^{14,15}. Many attempts have been made to adapt these techniques for issues with medical imaging, such as tumor segmentation and detection on CT images^{16,17,18,19}. The variability of the datasets, particularly when gathered from several centers²⁰, is a significant obstacle to building completely automated algorithms that can be used with any CT. Lung structures appear differently in CT images with various acquisition- or reconstruction settings. The approaches outlined in the existing literature typically don't include a CT preprocessing

module in the pipeline, which leaves the problem of data harmonization up to a data-driven approach that necessitates big datasets representing all facets of this inhomogeneity.

To place this model in the context of related published work, Kamal et al. (2018)¹⁷ segmented lung tumours using a Recurrent 3D-DenseUNet architecture, resulting in a DSC of 0.74 on a validation dataset of 40 patients. Jue et al. (2019)¹⁹ evaluated a number of 2D convolutional neural network (CNN) architectures to segment patches of 160x160 pixels centred on the tumour, achieving a DSC of 0.68 on the external validation dataset. These architectures included U-net, Segnet, full-resolution residual neural network (FRRN), and incremental multiple resolution residual neural network (MRRN). Despite the model's unfortunate lack of external validation, Zhang et al. (2020)²¹ used a modified version of ResNet to automatically segment GTV and attained an averaged dice similarity coefficient (DSC) of 0.73 on the test set. AUC of 94.4% was achieved by a deep learning-based software created by Ardila et al. (2019)¹⁶ that can identify lung cancer on low dose CT scans.

Code Implementation and Explanation

1. All the code as a whole

```
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from skimage.segmentation import clear_border
from skimage import measure
from skimage.measure import label, regionprops
from scipy import ndimage as ndi
from scipy.ndimage import measurements, center_of_mass, binary_dilation, zoom
import plotly.graph_objects as go
import pickle

# Open target data
filepath = "Lungseg.npy"
seg = np.load(filepath)

# CT's shape
print(seg.shape)

# Grey CT
plt.figure(figsize=(8,8))
plt.pcolormesh(seg[80], cmap='Greys_r')
```

```

# Normal CT
plt.pcolormesh(seg[80])

# Save img in a specific folder - Loop through to create the whole dataset images
for i in range(124):
    plt.pcolormesh(seg[i])
    if i < 1:
        plt.colorbar()
    plt.savefig(f"normal_CT/slice_{i}")

# Threshold mask -> for the air
mask = seg < -320
plt.pcolormesh(mask[80])

# Clear outer border with the clear_border function
mask = np.vectorize(clear_border, signature='(a,b)->(a,b)')(mask)
plt.pcolormesh(mask[80]) # => Outer border removed

# Separate image into volumes and assign them integer values using the Label
function
mask_region = np.vectorize(label, signature='(a,b)->(a,b)')(mask)
plt.pcolormesh(mask_region[80]) # regions based on different colors

# Sort out the regions' areas --> Guaranteed to keep the Lungs' areas --> For one
slide
slice = mask_region[50]
repr = regionprops(slice) # get regions' properties as a list
slice_areas = [i.area for i in repr] # All targeted slice's areas - area in
pixels
ind = np.argsort(slice_areas)[::-1] # Biggest to Smallest sort of areas

# Take the three largest areas for one slice --> Remove other smaller areas
slice = mask_region[50]
new_slice = np.zeros_like(slice)
print(repr[0].coords) # return a tuple of arrays containing the coordinates (y,x)
of all pixels that make up the region

for i in ind[:3]:
    new_slice[tuple(repr[i].coords.T)] = i + 1
plt.pcolormesh(new_slice)

# Take the three largest areas for all slides --> Remove other smaller areas

```

```

def large_three(slices):
    new_slices = np.zeros_like(slices)
    repr = regionprops(slices) # get regions' properties as a List
    slice_areas = [i.area for i in repr] # All targeted slice's areas - area in
pixels
    ind = np.argsort(slice_areas)[::-1] # Biggest to Smallest sort of areas
    for i in ind[:3]:
        new_slices[tuple(repr[i].coords.T)] = i + 1
    return new_slices

# Sort out the regions' areas --> For all slides
mask_region = np.vectorize(large_three, signature='(a,b)->(a,b)')(mask_region)
plt.pcolor(mesh(mask_region[100]))

# Fill all holes in the lung slices
mask = mask_region > 0 # Return a boolean array of Trues and Falses
plt.pcolor(mesh(mask[80]))

mask = np.vectorize(ndi.binary_fill_holes, signature='(a,b)->(a,b)')(mask) # Fill
all holes of all 124 slides
plt.pcolor(mesh(mask[80]))

# Remove small areas like the trachea, etc...
# In a 512x512 image, the trachea typically takes up less than 0.69% of the area.
We can delete all regions that have any area smaller than this percentage
def little_removal(slice, a=0.0069):
    new = slice.copy()
    region = label(slice, connectivity=1, background=0) # Separate the image into
different regions
    repr = regionprops(region)
    slice_areas = np.array([r.area for r in repr])
    ind = np.where(slice_areas/512**2 < a)[0]
    for i in ind:
        new[tuple(repr[i].coords.T)] = 0
    return new

mask = np.vectorize(little_removal, signature='(a,b)->(a,b)')(mask)
plt.pcolor(mesh(mask[80]))

# Lung area expansion by growing the border, with binary_dilation
mask = binary_dilation(mask, iterations=10) # Expansion based on the 'iteration'
argument

```

```

plt.pcolormesh(mask[80])

# Create a 3D plotly plot

# First, reduce the resolution
zoom_image = zoom(1*(mask), (0.4, 0.4, 0.4)) # Down to 40%
print(zoom_image.shape)

# Get arrays of x, y, and z. In a CT scan, the difference between pixels in the z
direction is about 4 times bigger than in the x and y directions:
z, x, y = [np.arange(i) for i in zoom_image.shape]
z *= 4

# Create a meshgrid
X, Y, Z = np.meshgrid(x,y,z, indexing='ij')

# 3D plotly plot and save as an interactive html file
def creat_plot(plot_name):
    fig = go.Figure(data=go.Volume(
        x=X.flatten(),
        y=Y.flatten(),
        z=Z.flatten(),
        value=np.transpose(zoom_image, (1,2,0)).flatten(),
        isomin=0.1,
        opacity=0.1, # needs to be small to see through all surfaces
        surface_count=10, # needs to be a large number for good volume rendering
    ))
    fig.write_html(f"{plot_name}")

creat_plot("dialation_10_v10.html")

# New image from the original image which only focus on the Lungs
new_img = mask * seg
plt.pcolormesh(new_img[80])

plt.colorbar() # Show color scale
plt.show()

```

2. Hounsfield Unit

The Hounsfield unit (HU) is a relative quantitative measurement of radio density used by radiologists in the interpretation of computed tomography (CT) images. The Hounsfield unit is calculated based on a linear transformation of the baseline linear attenuation coefficient of the X-ray beam, where distilled water is arbitrarily defined to be zero Hounsfield Units and air defined as -1000 HU²². This is the type of value used in the dataset's images to identify different materials which exist in the CT scans. Below is the HU formula:

$$HU(x, y) \equiv 1000 \cdot \frac{\mu(x, y) - \mu_{\text{water}}}{\mu_{\text{water}} - \mu_{\text{air}}}$$

Where μ is the linear attenuation coefficient of the material. The linear attenuation coefficient is defined based on how the intensity of a photon beam decays as it passes a distance x through a material. Note that depends on the energy of the photon beam, and in a CT scan photons usually have energies keV. Here are typical HU values: \approx

Substance		HU
Air		-1000
Fat		-120 to -90 ^[5]
Soft tissue on contrast CT		+100 to +300
Bone	Cancellous	+300 to +400 ^[6]
	Cortical	+500 to +1900 ^{[7][6][8]}
Subdural hematoma	First hours	+75 to +100 ^[9]
	After 3 days	+65 to +85 ^[9]
	After 10–14 days	+35 to +40 ^[10]
Other blood	Unclothed	+13 ^[11] to +50 ^[12]
	Clotted	+50 ^[13] to +75 ^{[11][13]}
Pleural effusion	Transudate	+2 to +15 ^[14]
	Exudate	+4 to +33 ^[14]
Other fluids	Chyle	-30 ^[15]
	Water	0
	Urine	-5 to +15 ^[5]
	Bile	-5 to +15 ^[5]
	CSF	+15
	Abscess / Pus	0 ^[16] or +20, ^[17] to +40 ^[17] or +45 ^[16]
	Mucus	0 ^[18] - 130 ^[19] ("high attenuating" at over 70 HU) ^{[20][21]}
Parenchyma	Lung	-700 to -600 ^[22]
	Kidney	+20 to +45 ^[5]
	Liver	60 ± 6 ^[23]
	Lymph nodes	+10 to +20 ^[24]
	Muscle	+35 to +55 ^[5]
	Thymus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • +20 to +40 in children^[25] • +20 to +120 in adolescents^[25]
	White matter	+20 to +30
	Grey matter	+37 to +45
Gallstone	Cholesterol stone	+30 to +100 ^[26]
	Bilirubin stone	+90 to +120 ^[26]
Foreign body ^[27]	Windowpane glass	+500
	Aluminum, tarmac, car window glass, bottle glass, and other rocks	+2,100 to +2,300
	Limestone	+2,800
	Copper	+14,000
	Silver	+17,000
	Steel	+20,000
	Gold, steel, and brass	+30,000 (upper measurable limit)
Earwax		<0

3. Steps

3.1. Setting up

```
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from skimage.segmentation import clear_border
from skimage import measure
from skimage.measure import label, regionprops
from scipy import ndimage as ndi
from scipy.ndimage import measurements, center_of_mass, binary_dilation, zoom
import plotly.graph_objects as go
import pickle
```

- Setting up the necessary libraries and functions, you can either do this by pip installing on cmd or specifically install via git clone

3.2. Open target data

```
# Open target data
filepath = "Lungseg.npy"
seg = np.load(filepath)
```

- Access the dataset of CT scan, this should be in your working directory, or you can specify it in the filepath, example: "C:\Python\working_folder"
- These libraries are compatible with numpy files, so you need to convert the initial CT images set all into a numpy file

3.3. See the CT's pixel shape

```
# CT's shape
print(seg.shape)
```

Output:

```
(124, 512, 512)
```

Explanation:

- The output is an array of 3 values: the first is the number of slices from the dataset (124), the second and third are the number of pixels which made up the 2D dimensions of each image, here is 512 pixels x 512 pixels

3.4. Grey CT

```
# Grey CT  
plt.pcolormesh(seg[80], cmap='Greys_r')
```

At the end of the code:

```
plt.colorbar() # Show HU's color bar  
plt.show()
```

Output:

(slide 80)

Explanation:

- The `plt.colormesh()` function is a BIF from the `Matplotlib` library imported above, it is used to create a pseudocolor plot with a non-regular rectangular grid, which takes in 3

parameters: x-coordinates, y-coordinates, and c - the values in a 2D array which are to be colored

- “seg” is the name of dataset’s array of CT slices, using list comprehension, slice 80 is selected
- The `plt.colorbar()` function adds a colorbar to the plot to indicate the color scale
- In order for the plot to show, the function `plt.show()` must be present after the desired plot

3.5. Regular CT

```
# Normal CT  
plt.pcolormesh(seg[80])
```

Output:

(slide 80)

Explanation:

- The lungs, tissues along with outer and inner air spaces are all visible in the outputted plot. This is the raw data and the first step to the lungs' segmentation process

3.6. Save all the output images into a specific folder

```
for i in range(124):
    plt.pcolormesh(seg[i])
    a = plt.colorbar()
    plt.savefig(f"outer_border_removed/slice_{i}")
    a.remove() # To remove the colorbar in the current, preparing for the next
plot
```

Output:

(all slides)

Explanation:

- By looping through all the “seg” slices via range() method and plt.savefig() function, all 124 processed images is located in the selected folder “normal_CT”
- Each colorbar declared in “plt.colorbar()” line is associated with last created plot of “plt.pcolormesh()”
- The command “a.remove()” is to remove the colorbar of the current existing plot in the “plt.pcolormesh(seg[i])” line. When the next plot is created, a new colorbar will be added
- This can work for any processed array of slices

3.7. Set the threshold mask to identify air spaces

```
# Threshold mask -> for the air
mask = seg < -320
plt.pcolormesh(mask[80])
```

Output:

(slide 80)

Explanation:

- Air is significantly less HU than other substances in the body, then apply a so-called "threshold" mask. Here, -320 HU is used as the lower limit
- The yellow areas are the air spaces
- Select out the areas with air is a preliminary step to segmenting the lungs
- Next up is removing the outer border of the image

3.8. Clear outer border

```
# Clear outer border with the clear_border function
mask = np.vectorize(clear_border, signature='(a,b)->(a,b)')(mask)
plt.pcolormesh(mask[80]) # => Outer border removed
```

Output:

(slide 80)

Explanation:

- `numpy.vectorize()` is a function that takes in a Python function and returns a new Python function that can take an array of values and apply the selected function to each element of the array. The output function is called a “vectorized” function because it can operate on an entire sequence of values at once, rather than iterating over each element
- Here, inside the `np.vectorize()` function, the `clear_border` function is used to clear the outer border of each of the 124 slices
- Take in a 2D array, return a 2D array. Or else, `np.vectorize` will return a 3D array

- Inside the `vectorize()` function, the “signature” parameter needs to be specified as `(a,b) → (a,b)` for the function to take in a 2D array, and return a 2D array. If not specified, the function will only return 3D arrays
- Now, only the inner parts (lungs, trachea) are visible

3.9. Separate the image into different regions with distinct values

Separate image into volumes and assign them integer values using the Label function

```
mask_region = np.vectorize(label, signature='(a,b)->(a,b)')(mask)  
plt.pcolormesh(mask_region[80]) # regions based on different colors
```

Output:

(slice 80)

Explain:

- The label function inside the `vectorize()` function separates the image into different regions along with their respective value (as shown in the colorbar)

3.10. Gather regions' areas and sort them out in order for one slice

```
# Sort out the regions' areas --> Guaranteed to keep the Lungs' areas --> For one slice
slice = mask_region[50]
repr = regionprops(slice) # get regions' properties as a list
slice_areas = [i.area for i in repr] # All targeted slice's areas - area in pixels
ind = np.argsort(slice_areas)[::-1] # Biggest to Smallest sort of areas
print(slice_areas)
print(ind)
```

Target:

(slice 50)

Output:

```
[38772.0, 30793.0, 281.0, 144.0]
[0 1 2 3]
```

Explanation:

- This is the starting step of the three step of getting the top three largest areas on selected CT scans. The target image is slice 50 taken from the previous label function
- This time, to have a better look, slice 50 which consists of four distinct regions is chosen rather instead of slice 80 which consists of three separate regions
Then, regionprops() function is used get all the slice regions' properties
- After that, select only the area volumes from the list of properties with shorthand list comprehension and store them in the "slice_areas" variable
- Finally, sort out the area by using numpy argsort() function, this return a list of values from smallest to largest. To continue further steps, a biggest to smallest values array is needed, so extra argument "[::-1]" to use to achieve the desired list
- The first output represents the four regions' areas of slice 50, while the second one indicate the indices of the largest to smallest values of the former list

3.11. Retain the three largest regions' areas and remove smaller ones for one slide

```
# Take the three largest areas for one slide --> Remove other smaller areas
slice = mask_region[50]
new_slice = np.zeros_like(slice)
print(repr[0].coords) # return a tuple of arrays containing the coordinates (y,x)
of all pixels that make up the region
print(type(repr[0].coords.T)) # return a tuple of arrays containing the
coordinates (y,x) of all pixels that make up the region, but transposed

for i in ind[:3]:
    new_slice[tuple(repr[i].coords.T)] = i + 1
plt.pcolormesh(new_slice)
```

Output:

```
[[ 71 154]
 [ 71 155]
 [ 71 156]
 ...
 [385 154]
 [385 155]
 [386 154]]
```

(result from “repr[0].coords” of slide 50)

```
[[ 71  71  71 ... 385 385 386]  
 [154 155 156 ... 154 155 154]]
```

(result from “repr[0].coords.T” of slide 50)

(slide 50 before and after removal except for the three largest areas)

Explanation:

- Firstly, create a “new_slice” by using `numpy.zeros_like()` function which will result in a slice of the shape and size as the original slice but only consists of 0 values
- To get a better understanding of what the line “repr[i].coords.T” does, we must take a closer look at “repr[0].coords”. “i” is replaced by 0 to get the properties, specifically the (y,x) coordinates that makes up the first region in slice 50. This is shown in the output above
- After that, the first region’s coordinates are transposed with “T” argument, result in “repr[0].coords.T” line, the output is a two-list array, one for y-coordinates and one for x-coordinates
- Next up is the loop, because the intended output are the three largest regions, “ind[:3]” list comprehension is used to iterate up to the third element in the “ind” array
- Now, the line “new_slice[tuple(repr[i].coords.T)] = i + 1” means to replace all the 0 elements in “new_slice” with new elements (1, 2, 3) in the order of (y,x) coordinates obtained with “repr[i].coords.T”
- For “i+1”, because 0 is the air’s value, each subsequence i number must be added with 1 to show distinct color value. Hence, the output is indicated by three largest regions of distinct color marks (1: first region, 2: second region, 3: third region, 0: air)

- The tuple function is used to change the (y,x) coordinates array type from “numpy.ndarray” to “tuple” for list comprehension

3.12. Retain the three largest regions' areas and remove smaller ones for all slides

```
# Sort out the regions' areas --> For all slides
def large_three(slices):
    new_slices = np.zeros_like(slices)
    repr = regionprops(slices) # get regions' properties as a List
    slice_areas = [i.area for i in repr] # ALL targeted slice's areas - area in
pixels
    ind = np.argsort(slice_areas)[::-1] # Biggest to Smallest sort of areas
    for i in ind[:3]:
        new_slices[tuple(repr[i].coords.T)] = i + 1
    return new_slices

mask_region = np.vectorize(large_three, signature='(a,b)->(a,b)')(mask_region)
plt.pcolormesh(mask_region[100])
```

Output:

(slide 100 before and after region removal)

Explanation:

- The last sections have explained the component functions used in this process to keep the three regions with the largest areas while discarding the rest.
- This is done firstly by creating a copy variable of the selected sequence of slices
- Follow-up steps are the same as the previous part: get regions' properties, then sort the area properties of those regions in descending order
- Then, exchange the 0 elements in new_slices with i values (1,2,3), as explained in the previous part
- Finally, np.vectorize() is used with the newly created "large_three" function to remove smaller areas except for the three largest of all 124 CT slices

3.13. Fill holes in the lung slices

```
# Fill all holes in the lung slices
```

```
mask = mask_region > 0 # Return a boolean array of Trues and Falses
```

```
plt.pcolormesh(mask[80])
```

```
mask = np.vectorize(ndi.binary_fill_holes, signature='(a,b)->(a,b)')(mask) # Fill  
all holes of all 124 slides
```

```
plt.pcolormesh(mask[80])
```

Output:

(slide 80 before and after holes filling)

Explanation:

- The "mask" variable return an array of boolean values (True – space, False – empty)

- Using ndimage from the scipy library, “ndimage.binary_fill_holes” to fill all False values’ spaces

3.14. Remove small unnecessary areas

Remove small areas like the trachea, etc...

```
def little_removal(slice, a=0.0069):
    new = slice.copy()
    region = label(slice, connectivity=1, background=0) # Separate the image into
different regions
    repr = regionprops(region)
    slice_areas = np.array([r.area for r in repr])
    ind = np.where(slice_areas/512**2 < a)[0]
    for i in ind:
        new[tuple(repr[i].coords.T)] = 0
    return new
```

```
mask = np.vectorize(little_removal, signature='(a,b)->(a,b)')(mask)
plt.pcolormesh(mask[80])
```

Output:

(slide 80 before and after trachea removal)

Explanation:

- Since the purpose of this method is only the lungs segmentation, smaller areas such as bones, trachea need to be removed

- In a 512x512 image, the trachea typically takes up less than 0.69% of the area. We can delete all regions that have any area smaller than this percentage
- Here, a new function called “little_removal” is created, it takes in a slice along with the percentage of smaller areas needed to be removed.
- Then, the function makes a “new” copy of the input slice
- “region” variable is the array of different regions from the input slice by applying the label() function
- From that “region” variable, the function take its area properties and put them in a numpy array variable called “slice_areas”
- Following that, “ind” variable will take in all the indices from “slice_areas” where the area percentage is lower than 0.69%
- For the loop, the sample process as the “large_three” loop but this time, rather exchanging the 0 elements with something else, “little_removal” will replace the smaller areas’ values with 0. This will make those areas values the same as air, making them disappear from the final output
- Finally, call np.vectorize() funtion to remove all small areas of 124 slices

3.15. Expand the lung area

```
# Lung area expansion by growing the border, with binary_dilation
mask = binary_dilation(mask, iterations=10) # Expansion based on the 'iteration'
argument
plt.pcolormesh(mask[80])
```

Output:

Explanation:

- `binary_dilation()` can grow the border of the lung areas, depends on the “iterations” argument

3.16. Create a 3D plotly plot

3.16a. Resolution reduction

```
# First, reduce the resolution
zoom_image = zoom(1*(mask), (0.4, 0.4, 0.4)) # Down to 40%
print(zoom_image.shape)
```

Output:

```
(50, 205, 205)
```

Explanation:

- To make the plot more interactive and require less computing power, the images resolution must be reduced
- In this instance, `zoom()` function is used to reduce the images resolution to 40%, making the shape fall from ‘124 x 512 x 512’ to ‘50 x 205 x 205’

3.16b. Get arrays of x, y and z

```
# Get arrays of x, y, and z
z, x, y = [np.arange(i) for i in zoom_image.shape]
z *= 4
```

Explanation:

- Arrange the “`zoom_image.shape`” as arrays of z, x and y
- In a CT scan, the difference between pixels in the z direction is about 4 times bigger than in the x and y directions, so z is multiplied by 4. This is for plotting in plotly

3.16c. Create a meshgrid

```
# Create a meshgrid
X, Y, Z = np.meshgrid(x,y,z, indexing='ij')
```

- From the arrays of x, y and z, a meshgrid is constructed with indexing of “ij”
- The indexing arguments indicates which indexing convention is used, in this case, “ij” means the resulting matrix is in the form of matrix indexing

3.16d. Create the interactive 3D plot

```
def creat_plot(plot_name):
    fig = go.Figure(data=go.Volume(
```

```

x=X.flatten(),
y=Y.flatten(),
z=Z.flatten(),
value=np.transpose(zoom_image,(1,2,0)).flatten(),
isomin=0.1,
opacity=0.1, # needs to be small to see through all surfaces
surface_count=10, # needs to be a large number for good volume rendering
))
fig.write_html(f"{plot_name}")

```

```

creat_plot("dialation_10_v10.html")

```

Output:

(plot_1a)

☐ Ⓜ Ⓡ Ⓢ Ⓣ Ⓤ Ⓥ Ⓦ Ⓧ Ⓨ Ⓩ

(plot_1b)

☐ Ⓜ Ⓡ Ⓢ Ⓣ Ⓤ Ⓥ Ⓦ Ⓧ Ⓨ Ⓩ

(plot_1c)

(plot_1d)

Explanation:

- X.flatten(), Y.flatten(), Z.flatten() are to return the copies of those arrays collapsed into one dimension, from 3D meshgrids to one dimensional ones
- zoom_image is also needed to be flattened
- Configure the arguments: opacity for transparency and surface_count for volume rendering
- After calling create_plot() function along with “plot_name” argument, an interactive html file will be created, press on it and choose the suitable web browser to see the plot

3.17. Lung segmentation

```
# New image from the original image which only focus on the Lungs
new_img = mask * seg
plt.pcolormesh(new_img[80])
```

Output:

(slice 80 from the beginning versus only the lungs)

Explanation:

- This is the final result, the lungs segmentation by multiplying the mask and the original image

Result/Conclusion

Result

Original images versus the final results of lungs segmentation

(slice 50 from the beginning versus final result)

(slice 80 from the beginning versus final result)

(slice 80 from the beginning versus final result)

Conclusion

State-of-the-art NSCLC detection and 3D volumetric segmentation on CT scans can be accomplished with this deep learning-based method. Despite the fact that there have been other attempts to create algorithms for lung cancer CT detection and segmentation, this work remains unique, particularly in that it has undergone external validation and can operate on complete thoracic CT scans without requiring additional input from a human operator. When compared to experts, the suggested procedure is more rapid and repeatable. In addition, radiologists and radiation oncologists favored automated segmentations in 56% of the instances on average. Furthermore, the tumor volumes are measured and RECIST criteria are applied to assess the prognostic potential of the automated contours. In contrast to approaches based on manual outlines, segmentations made using this method divided patients into low and high survival groups with more relevance. The method and codes can be used for any datasets of CT scans,

specifically a region of interest (ROI), such as lungs, heart, etc... One can create a mask of an object and then can detect, segment, build it further, all automatically.

Dataset

The dataset set used in this paper is publicly available on Kaggle and can be accessed with the following source:

<https://www.kaggle.com/code/redwankarimsony/rsna-str-3d-stacking-3d-plot-segmentation/output>

Reference

1. Bray, F., Ferlay, J., Soerjomataram, I., Siegel, R.L., Torre, L.A. and Jemal, A., 2018. Global cancer statistics 2018: GLOBOCAN estimates of incidence and mortality worldwide for 36 cancers in 185 countries. *CA: a cancer journal for clinicians*, 68(6), pp.394-424.
2. Postmus, P.E., Kerr, K.M., Oudkerk, M., Senan, S., Waller, D.A., Vansteenkiste, J., Escriu, C. and Peters, S., 2017. Early and locally advanced non-small-cell lung cancer (NSCLC): ESMO Clinical Practice Guidelines for diagnosis, treatment and follow-up. *Annals of oncology*, 28, pp.iv1-iv21.
3. Jaffray, D.A., 2012. Image-guided radiotherapy: from current concept to future perspectives. *Nature reviews Clinical oncology*, 9(12), pp.688-699.
4. Barrett, A., Dobbs, J. & Roques, T. (2009) Practical Radiotherapy Planning. 4th edn. CRC Press.
5. Stroom, J.C. and Heijmen, B.J., 2002. Geometrical uncertainties, radiotherapy planning margins, and the ICRU-62 report. *Radiotherapy and oncology*, 64(1), pp.75-83.
6. Wolchok, J.D., Hoos, A., O'Day, S., Weber, J.S., Hamid, O., Lebbé, C., Maio, M., Binder, M., Bohnsack, O., Nichol, G. and Humphrey, R., 2009. Guidelines for the evaluation of immune therapy activity in solid tumors: immune-related response criteria. *Clinical cancer research*, 15(23), pp.7412-7420.
7. Erasmus, J.J., Gladish, G.W., Broemeling, L., Sabloff, B.S., Truong, M.T., Herbst, R.S. and Munden, R.F., 2003. Interobserver and intraobserver variability in measurement of non-small-cell carcinoma lung lesions: implications for assessment of tumor response. *Journal of clinical oncology*, 21(13), pp.2574-2582.
8. Lambin, P., Rios-Velazquez, E., Leijenaar, R., Carvalho, S., Van Stiphout, R.G., Granton, P., Zegers, C.M., Gillies, R., Boellard, R., Dekker, A. and Aerts, H.J.,

2012. Radiomics: extracting more information from medical images using advanced feature analysis. *European journal of cancer*, 48(4), pp.441-446.
9. Lambin, P., Leijenaar, R.T., Deist, T.M., Peerlings, J., De Jong, E.E., Van Timmeren, J., Sanduleanu, S., Larue, R.T., Even, A.J., Jochems, A. and van Wijk, Y., 2017. Radiomics: the bridge between medical imaging and personalized medicine. *Nature reviews Clinical oncology*, 14(12), pp.749-762.
 10. Aerts, H.J., Velazquez, E.R., Leijenaar, R.T., Parmar, C., Grossmann, P., Carvalho, S., Bussink, J., Monshouwer, R., Haibe-Kains, B., Rietveld, D. and Hoebers, F., 2014. Decoding tumour phenotype by noninvasive imaging using a quantitative radiomics approach. *Nature communications*, 5(1), p.4006.
 11. Kumar, V., Gu, Y., Basu, S., Berglund, A., Eschrich, S.A., Schabath, M.B., Forster, K., Aerts, H.J., Dekker, A., Fenstermacher, D. and Goldgof, D.B., 2012. Radiomics: the process and the challenges. *Magnetic resonance imaging*, 30(9), pp.1234-1248.
 12. Ibrahim, A., et al., 2019. Radiomics analysis for clinical decision support in nuclear medicine. *Semin. Nucl. Med.*,
<https://doi.org/10.1053/j.semnuclmed.2019.06.005>.
 13. Kalmet, P.H., Sanduleanu, S., Primakov, S., Wu, G., Jochems, A., Refaee, T., Ibrahim, A., Hulst, L.V., Lambin, P. and Poeze, M., 2020. Deep learning in fracture detection: a narrative review. *Acta orthopaedica*, 91(2), pp.215-220.
 14. Ronneberger, O., Fischer, P., and Brox, T., 2015. U-Net: Convolutional Networks for Biomedical Image Segmentation. *Lect. Notes Comput. Sci.*,
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-24574-4_28.
 15. Szegedy, C., et al., 2015. Going deeper with convolutions. 2015 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR),
<https://doi.org/10.1109/cvpr.2015.7298594>.
 16. Ardila, D., Kiraly, A.P., Bharadwaj, S., Choi, B., Reicher, J.J., Peng, L., Tse, D., Etemadi, M., Ye, W., Corrado, G. and Naidich, D.P., 2019. End-to-end lung cancer screening with three-dimensional deep learning on low-dose chest computed tomography. *Nature medicine*, 25(6), pp.954-961.
 17. Kamal, U., Rafi, A.M., Hoque, R., Wu, J., and Hasan, M.K., 2020. Lung cancer tumor region segmentation using recurrent 3D-DenseUNet. *Thoracic Image Analysis*, pp.36–47 https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-62469-9_4.
 18. Ray, A., 2016. Lung Tumor Segmentation via Fully Convolutional Neural Networks. Stanford University, CS 231N, Winter.
 19. Jiang, J., Hu, Y.C., Liu, C.J., Halpenny, D., Hellmann, M.D., Deasy, J.O., Mageras, G. and Veeraraghavan, H., 2018. Multiple resolution residually connected feature streams for automatic lung tumor segmentation from CT images. *IEEE transactions on medical imaging*, 38(1), pp.134-144.
 20. Mackin, D., Fave, X., Zhang, L., Fried, D., Yang, J., Taylor, B., Rodriguez-Rivera, E., Dodge, C. and Jones, A.K., Court L. 2015. Measuring Computed Tomography Scanner Variability of Radiomics Features. *Invest Radiol*, 50, pp.1-9.

21. Zhang, F., Wang, Q. and Li, H., 2020. Automatic segmentation of the gross target volume in non-small cell lung cancer using a modified version of ResNet. *Technology in Cancer Research & Treatment*, 19, p.1533033820947484.
22. DenOtter TD, Schubert J. Hounsfield Unit. 2023 Mar 6. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2023 Jan-. PMID: 31613501.
23. Primakov, S.P., Ibrahim, A., van Timmeren, J.E., et al., 2022. Automated detection and segmentation of non-small cell lung cancer computed tomography images. *Nat Commun* 13, 3423 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-30841-3>.